

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND ITS IMPACT ON JOB SATISFACTION - A STUDY OF BANKING EMPLOYEES

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Abstract

Presently the banking sector is one of the rapidly moving sectors for customer service in Indian economical aspect. In the beginning of Independence, the banking sector was completely controlled or under impression and influence of Chief Bureaucrats and because of this very less number of banking service institutions were existing. By the passages of time there has been observed a long lasting formation of banking sector because of introduction of privatization and liberalization and that is why the banking sector has grown rapidly. Even after having such enlarged sector a very limited studies has been observed on impact on satisfaction of job through emotional intelligence far as the bank employs are concerned. The word emotional intelligence includes various components of it such as awareness of self or called self awareness, self motivation, and skills of social nature and also includes social regulation. The job satisfaction is a kind of the term which provides a sense of motivation to employees including the different aspects such as the job security, handsome remunerative packages, various rewards, better nature of work, benefit of leaves, a good working environment, the job rotation and job enlargement and the various different measures which has been imposed by different statutory provisions and has been implemented by the organizations and the governments. However as far as the bank employs and their job satisfaction are concerned. The proper measures have not been taken especially those advices which have been given by banking sector experts for ensuring proper job satisfaction. Undoubtedly the measures which are adopted for the job satisfaction are the key contributory mechanisms which help in keeping employees healthy, happy and efficient. With the help of job satisfaction of the employees of the banking system the better customer services can be provided. In the banking operations management can influentially encounter the other aspects the bank management and can also focus on promoting and providing better opportunities for developing the social and interpersonal skills in their employees and building a good relationship mechanism between the workers and could help to fill up the needs of the employees in different recreational activities. Hence it has been suggested and recommended that the better potential of employees relating to emotional intelligence can be helpful in developing job satisfaction among the bank employees. The present study has an attempt of making analysis about intelligence level of emotional nature, and satisfaction of employees as far as job is concerned in banking sector, because as such a linking of job satisfaction and emotional intelligence is not available in any previous studies.

Keywords: Intelligence, Satisfaction, Efficiency, Employees, Emotional, Relationship, Environment, Banking.

INTRODUCTION

Various measures lead into the job satisfaction generally includes factors such as promotion or bonus or recreational facilities, medical facilities, increments, education to the child of employees and to some extent the housing facility. Most of the banking institutions provide only those job satisfaction facilities which are required by the statutory provisions but some of the banking institutions provides more than required by the statutory provisions. With the view to make improvement in the job satisfaction level of their employees, adopting a positive emotional intelligence level and obtaining better results especially in high productivity areas of banking operations requires.

However a general observation says that the level of satisfaction of employees of the bank may differ because of the fact that employees of some of the institutions are satisfied with the existing measures relating to the job satisfaction and employees of banking situations may not be satisfied with the measures adopted by their bank. Hence it becomes quite difficult for adopting any universal measurement criteria for job satisfaction and any universal policy.

The management of banking institutions or different banks are expected to have a specifically designed job satisfaction policy in consultation with their employees. Another factor which is quite worthy to note here is that the behaviour and attitude of employees towards job satisfaction measures has changed drastically in the last two decades. In the few years the measures or methods adopted for the job satisfaction has gained immense popularity and consideration.

This might be because of need of emotional intelligence between the employees which has enlarged and enhanced due to better competition and a force and pressure for acquiring more customers and providing better customer service. One of the study which has been undertaken on importance of job satisfaction methods in banking sector and applicability of Factories Act on banking institutions has concluded that the management of banking institutions must give a focus on different measures adopted for job satisfaction for their employees so that emotional intelligence level can be improved.

Level of intelligence of emotional nature is always aimed to make human force enable in utilising their capabilities and caliber more efficiently and effectively. Undoubtedly in most of the organisation especially in banking industry, one of the major threat is the labour problem and since they provide public service hence their responsibility towards public enhances and this requires banking institutions to tackle their labour issues very wisely. Because of increasing cut throat competition among the banking sector and current depressing economical conditions employees have been forced to work for more hours with compulsory overtime which has increased the dissatisfaction level and stress level among the employees which ultimately resulting in lowering down their morale.

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND ITS IMPLICATIONS IN BANKING SECTOR

In this contemporary era undoubtedly the emotional intelligence level is a key factor for developing and announcing the capabilities and caliber of employees of bank such as their motivation, reasoning, empathy, management of conflict and communication skills. This all helps in enabling and understanding the enhancement of level among the employees to a very significant level. Emotional intelligence is undoubtedly very important especially as far as the administration of banks are concerned which is required for making it possible to generate satisfaction among the employees especially when management is concerned with the emotions of their employees. Undoubtedly emotional intelligence is a kind of tool which generates and drives a positive energy in their employees and which has made it possible for employees to fill up the gap between employees and management. Also emotional intelligence is very important factor for strengthening the moral and code of ethics in the banking system and it also provides a pattern for developing a higher level of protection of public investments and public money which creates a kind of safe net of development of welfare. The term emotional intelligence was first introduced in 1990 by

psychologist Mayer and Salovi, who has shown in their research that for improvement in the capacities in processing and perceiving the thoughts of employee's regulation of emotional intelligence level with accuracy and efficiency is very much important. Apart from all this the emotional intelligence also helps in building success in the environment of the business which ultimately strengthen the mental attitude of employees such as developing and making improvement in interpersonal communication skills, the social relationships and skills of decision making. It also helps in drawing better strategies for personal and professional life of employees. Undoubtedly emotional intelligence has a significant role in developing and forming a strong nature of relationship for employee's welfare and development in the banking industry. It develops a kind of leadership capabilities in the top management and helps the bottom level employees to better manage their emotional intelligence. In short it helps in both the levels to develop a better management opportunity. If we talk generally then emotional intelligence is a kind of tool which helps in developing the capability of someone with the help of proper training. This could help employees to recognise their own capacities and knowledge, their thoughts and behaviours in a better way so that they can have a positive relationship development with the customers of banks.

The emotional intelligence gives a kind of recharge to the positive energy level and employees undoubtedly are more keen to work in such an environment where more facilities are provided to the employees considering the cost effectiveness and that also standardises the pattern of working with the standardised structure. Hence nowadays the banks are working a lot on developing and practising their employees to develop their life for working under a customised emotional intelligence system. When the employees are satisfied the maintains a very straight relationship with their life within and outside the organisation and that is why most of the studies and their results has shown that when employees do not have job satisfaction especially in the field of banking sector they have a poor working efficiency and that is why it is strongly recommended to a positive emotional intelligence level so that job satisfaction level of bank employees can be improved and banks shall adopt proper methods for developing appropriate emotional intelligence of their employees. A strong mechanism and structure is required to enable the banks and their employee's satisfaction so the abilities of removing out the work stress among the bank employees can be adopted and banking operations can be improved. The emotional intelligence undoubtedly plays a very optimistic part in improving and enhancing the moral and absenteeism reduction which ultimately helps in improvement of job satisfaction of bank employees.

In the coming future the emotional intelligence will going to be a prime factor in the different dynamic structure of job satisfaction and this will play a significant role in generating better opportunities for banking sector employees. Nowadays the banks are continuously upgrading their mechanism for understanding of emotional intelligence of their employees by proper trainings to their management and employees so that both can workout together to tackle emotional intelligence issues, for promoting the goals of their bank and objectives by putting more vibrantly better performance structure. The banks is undertaken better value of emotional intelligence in significant manner so that it can develop better strategies to enable the level of emotional intelligence so that they can perform at the highest level if they will perform well they must be rewarded.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Abhijit faye They have indicated in their study that emotional intelligence broadly covers self awareness, emotion control, motivating own and a part of empathy. They all are very important for handling the relationship of employees with the management in an organisation. They have also observed that around 71% of total employees do not have good emotional intelligence level. As far as the self assessment is concerned they have also observed that as compared to unmarried employees married employees have good level of confidence. Here it will going to be very interesting to note that those employees having some kind of problems at their family are found to be having a higher level of feelings and emotions.

Chaudhary and Osman They have made an examination of correlation as existing between level of intelligence of emotion and performance of employees in Pakistan. In their study they have highlighted that employees always gives a higher level of performance when their emotional intelligence level is very high and that is why the organisation prefers such employees to recruit so that they can maintain performance of their labour force.

Deepanjana varshnay The manufacturing sector of India has explored in their study for relationship as between perception of employees for their organisation and the job satisfaction level and they have also made an examination of the role of involvement of mediators for developing the good relationships. In this study they have observed that the employees accept their company as an organisation where they can learn and exhibit a larger job involvement process and a higher level of satisfaction of job through development of better human resource policies with an expanded employee's involvement in the job this also ensures effective productivity of performance of employees.

Katuwal and Shyam Bhattur An study has been conducted by the researcher on textile workers in Nepal and they observe that a very high level of dissatisfaction is existing among the employees as far as the monetary expenditures made by organisation on employees are concerned. They are also found dissatisfied because of various behavioural and welfare facilities. In their study they have recommended that the satisfaction level of employees for their job arises or depends broadly on various facilities provided by organisation to their employees and the respect given by them to employees the welfare is given to the employees are also very important.

Mathur Daniel Goleman They are observed in their Study that there is an interlinking between the working environment and the emotional intelligence level. The level of intelligence of emotion is decided on the basis of the working environment which develops a very basic level of understanding among the employees and also develops an idea for handling different critical issues in better effective and efficient manner so that the work efficiency can be increased.

Radhika Kapoor He has shown in his study that the satisfaction at the job is undoubtedly a very crucial part for the working of the management of any organisation which makes enable the complete skilled workforce in managing the most critical circumstances. Undoubtedly it is quite understandable that the work nature, the care of organisation, a management for their employees, the benefits in form of salary and compensation, the working environment, the social relationship of employees with each other, various available opportunities at other places, the policies which are

adopted by the companies, the level of knowledge to employees and the method of resolution of conflicts or some of the factors which influence the jobs of employees.

Yashodara An study has been conducted by the researcher with the name of emotional intelligence and self-concept of bachelor's education students. The study has revealed that the Bachelors of Education students are significantly impacted and found different from other steam students. Further the study has also observed that they are found as such no difference in level of emotional intelligence between the B.Ed students and students of other schemes and also been cleared that emotional intelligence aspects are different for female students and male students.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study has been undertaken with the objective to describe various social economical, personal and emotional intelligence factors on various job satisfaction levels of employees. This is going to help in discussing the overall picture of level of intelligence of emotion of employees of the banks and how its relationship exists with satisfaction of Job. The study will further elaborate and analyse various characteristics of emotional intelligence in different categories such as awareness of self level, regulation of self control and skills of social nature and different aspects which could influence job satisfaction, factors such as personal factors or factors relating to promotion, family and social. The researcher expects that the study will going to helpful in suggesting to various banking institutions their employees as well as the government and policy makers to draw adequate policies

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The analytical study which has been undertaken in the present research is found to be the best fit in such kind of the studies. The researchers collected primary data from the different employees of the different banks. The secondary data has been collected from different sources such as the records of the government, various published and reference books, journals and newspapers and Internet sources. A sample of 200 employees consisting of 75 managerial level employees and 125 subordinate level employees from public banks has been collected and in the same way a sample of 200 employees consisting 72 employees from managerial level and 128 subordinate level employees from private sector banks have been collected. With the help of a stratified random sampling method the sample have been taken liquor 5 point scaling technique has been used for making an assortment of level of intelligence of emotion and satisfaction of job of bank employees has been undertaken.

Hypothesis for the Study

H ₀	There found existing no relationship between emotional intelligence and Job satisfaction among the bank employees
H ₁	There found existing relationship between emotional intelligence and Job satisfaction among the bank employees

Source of Data

As we discussed earlier, that data has been collected from bank employees for the period from January to July 2022, using a predesigned questionnaire. After analysis or scrutiny of the data, the researcher has rechecked the data by visiting the bank branches again to fill up the gaps in the questionnaires. We have collected data of secondary nature from the reports published in different sources such as banks,

Reserve bank of India, IRD reports and various bulletin books. The researcher has also reviewed many books and literature which has been published relating to the intelligence level of emotion and satisfaction of Job level. The data which has been collected has been verified analysed tabulated and summarised and using different methods or tools of statistical nature, the interpretations has been observed from the data

Data Analysis

For the purpose of the analysis of the data SPSS software has been used and one way Anova test independent sample T test and correlation and linear regression analysis have been used.

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Table 1: Results of Independent Samples T-Test for Factors of Emotional Intelligence having influence on Job Satisfaction

Factors of Emotional Intelligence		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means		
		F	Sig.	T	df	Sig. (2- tailed)
Personal Factors	Equal variances assumed	0.125	0.618	-1.217	400	0.248
Social Factors	Equal variances assumed	0.787	0.318	-2.111	400	0.039*
Promotional Factors	Equal variances assumed	0.218	0.689	-1.071	400	0.291
Family Factors	Equal variances assumed	0.217	0.615	0.187	400	0.876

Note: Computed from primary data

From the Table 1, we can observe that social factors ($t = -2.111$, $p = 0.039$) has observed to be having a significant impact at the gender level at significance level of 5 percent. Hence the researcher concludes that social factors generally use to have significant influence on job satisfaction level. Here it is also observed that job satisfaction is also highly dependent on the emotional intelligence by all factors of Emotional intelligence but majorily by social factors.

Table 2: Factors of Emotional Intelligence having influence on Job Satisfaction – ANOVA TEST

Factors influencing of Job Satisfaction		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Personal Factors	Between Groups	7.597	3	3.891	15.892	0.000*
	Within Groups	78.798	337	0.132		
	Total	86.395	340			
Social Factors	Between Groups	0.268	3	0.193	0.418	0.661
	Within Groups	106.128	337	0.298		
	Total	106.396	340			
Promotional Factors	Between Groups	3.287	3	1.748	4.108	0.016*
	Within Groups	121.187	337	0.965		
	Total	124.474	340			
Family Factors	Between Groups	0.038	3	0.018	0.053	0.953
	Within Groups	107.596	337	0.465		
	Total	107.634	340			

Note: Computed from primary data

Job Satisfaction is measured on the basis of the emotional intelligence has been evaluated in the table 2 above with consideration of rules of ANOVA Test. As shown in table 2, personal factors ($F_{3, 337} = 15.982, p < 0.05$). Same as social factors ($F_{3, 337} = 0.418, p < 0.05$) has been observed to be more satisfactory at the significance level of 5 as far as satisfaction from job is concerned for bank employees. Hence we can say that it has been observed that there existing a very important and significant correlation between various personal nature and Promotional nature factors with level of intelligence of emotion in case of various employees of Banks.

CONCLUSION

In today's competitive world undoubtedly banks role is quite significant as it provides a wide range of services with latest technology to their customers. With the modernization in the banking structure there have been come out various issues to their customers as well as to their employees such as giving them a time bound service, no misstatements in the information, no fraudulent activities and there should be no conflict between the employees and the customers. This is how the banks are now working and scaling up their employees attitude and performance towards a healthy and positive approach by working on developing a mechanism for emotional intelligence, so that they can deal with their customers in managing the difficult circumstances, to control employees of the bank and their emotional intelligence. Establishment undoubtedly promotes a very user friendly kind of service of banking through their employees. By having this improved intelligence of emotions also gives a kind of secured and satisfactory environment to their employees with the innovation of new technologies in the banking sector and the changing working pattern has developed various new working culture as between the bank employees, so that they can work without any difficulties and the abortion intelligence can also be maintained between the bank employees inefficient and effective manner.

SUGGESTIONS

1. The RBI required to take various actions so that the banks can establish better modern and centralised management programmes for emotional intelligence management in the form of training to public and private sector bank employees so that job satisfaction can be enabled.
2. The banks need to focus on various services or welfare related activities for employees at all levels of employees.
3. The government shall put efforts for ensuring better system of emotional intelligence and employee's job satisfaction pattern by appointment of a noodle officer so that he can streamline the existing mechanism of emotional intelligence and its line-up with job satisfaction.
4. The banks shall conduct various training programmes on regular Intervals so that employees can rebuild their knowledge and can recover from the stress arising from the working.
5. The governments and banks should provide a common space for various welfare activities such as yoga and meditation so the stress relief exercise can be undertaken at workplace.

6. The government also needs to take various appropriate actions such as granting special leaves and giving benefits for developing a working environment which is stress less.
7. The government as well as the bank need to provide proper transportation facility calls their employees so that they can reach their workplace in an easy and user friendly manner.

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